

Looking for a Community.

The word community is defined by the Oxford English dictionary as a group of people connected by a shared location, interest or characteristic.

I have since drawn very close interest in the word community by definition and by perception. The common man views community as my tribesmen or simply as my immediate local neighbors. When you dissect closely at the three variables, that is location, interest, and characteristic, then you realize that your “community” is probably not a community in most cases. You probably share just the location, not the interests and characteristics.

My experience with the community could not be a true reflection of the ideal situation all over, but it cuts across the vast majority, especially in the rural and/ or remote areas.

Born and raised in the village, Ugambe village, Sega, North Ugenya, Siaya County, I have seen most of the village life than urban life actually. I don't regret being a village boy in my childhood and teenage because that is my home where my umbilical cord was buried and still where I shall be rested on my last day of fate. However, the experiences I have had with the village has made me have a change in perception from the position I had earlier, pledging to live by the village and do everything that it takes from there. It's obvious that I was too young to know and understand whatever happened in the early years of my growth and development, but I have a clear picture of a number of events most of which would not encourage anyone to be there unless otherwise.

Cases Studies

In the 80s, about 40 goats were burned in my grandfather's cow shed. It's alleged that someone of bad will set up the fire. Otherwise, where did it come from anyway, since there was no other cause at that time. There was no form of electricity in that home or even in closer proximity, additionally, nobody used to cook in the shed as there were designated kitchen points, and actually much of cooking was done outside in the open air.

In the 90s, a number of cows were stolen belonging to one of my mothers. At that time, that was a big blow to her since that was her source of milk which she traded on. She almost committed suicide owing to the same.

In 2005, someone broke into the kitchen and walked away with the chicken and the basics including simple assets like sufurias and drums. This was very petty.

In 2013, 2016, and probably 2018, not very clear memory on this since it has happened more than this, chicken were stolen from my mother's kitchen where they used to reside. In all the cases, all the chicken were taken away.

In 2017, 2018, and other subsequent years, farm produce, maize to be more specific and at times groundnuts were harvested from my mother's farms. This has been a very common routine since then, and it happens almost every season of harvesting.

In 2019, all the cows were taken from my father's cow shed plus the sheep. About 7 cows and I think 2 sheep. I still remember the call I received from mzee in his hoarse voice at 6am,

feeling so defeated and indeed he was, because since then we never brought in any cows to that shed.

Banana farm established with very high reputation by mzee has since fallen down because we could honestly not maintain a farm where the owner harvests 30 percent and the thieves harvest the rest 70 percent. This goes on to date.

In 2023, someone harvested about 2 sacks of maize from our main farm, leaving my mother in disbelief, she cried in my presence. This probably was the first time after her husband's demise, seeing her that weak, hopeless and helpless. I had to relax her down though I did not even know how to do it.

In 2025, having cultivated sweet potatoes in about one acre of land, and expecting the highest harvest for the very first time, since the weather was on my side with enough rains. I had tried this before, unsuccessfully because there was drought throughout the season, that was 2020 or 2021. My potatoes this time did extremely well, but was harvested by the "owners" more than the owners. At this time, the thieves were even seen walking away with the potatoes, some were seen harvesting in broad daylight.

These are just but a few practical examples of the many cases of witnessed theft in that area. I have since found a number of these people red handed in my farms but no legal action has yielded anything. Some if not all, being my relatives, though distant, and so my elders discourage any legal pursuit, despite myself trying to take that direction. I have found someone cut my bananas in the farm, I have found someone in my fruit farm on top ready to harvest.

The problem is that even those reported from other areas have since been left and are with us in the village. Some have been sued for more serious cases and served their terms, back to the village unreformed.

Conclusion

In summary, my village is not viable for a developer, a person with a mentality that is change oriented. Someone goes to steal a window of a new house under construction even before the owner starts living there. I mean, it's a high degree of shame. The local authorities dive with these guys in the same sea in most cases, but the investor suffers. Shops broken into, and this happens over time. The fact that it has been happening since the early 80s according to my history, to date, when its actually worse, only implies that it is something not going to change anytime soon.

I chose not to sue constantly, but also not to struggle with helping such people who can never reform.in fact the help you grant them is a ticket to show that you are abled and so its worth robbing you.

Does this paper answer the question of why people grow in the village, get enlightened and move out to settle in different places, to form new communities? After all, you have to keep looking for people who match your interests and characteristics.

Author: Dr. Okong'o Ouma. A